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Basic motor competencies and the amount of physical education in European primary school children

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ABSTRACT

Children show large differences in their basic motor competencies (BMC), which are key learning objectives of physical education (PE) and serve as a foundation for participating in school-based and extracurricular sports. While individual determinants, including age, sex, and extracurricular physical activity, are known to consistently predict BMC, studies investigating the role of structural aspects of PE on children's BMC levels are lacking. This study examined whether weekly PE time is associated with differences in BMC levels in children across Europe, beyond individual factors. Endogenous (age, sex, body-mass-index), exogenous (participation in ball or individual sports) and structural factors (amount of weekly PE) along with BMC values (*object movement* and *self-movement*, tested with the MOBAK-1–2 and MOBAK-3–4) were assessed in 4291 6- to 10-year-old children (50 % girls) in twelve European countries. Hierarchical regression models revealed that individual factors were consistent predictors of BMC, but no associations were found between the amount of PE and BMC. These results indicate that other PE aspects may be more indicative of differences in BMC than the amount of PE. The significant role of extracurricular sports underscores the importance of analysing and promoting the availability of such activities.

KEYWORDS

Time allocation; extracurricular physical activity; learning objectives; motor competence; aspects of teaching

Introduction

Physical education (PE) in primary school is regarded as an optimal period for children to develop and enhance their motor competence, which supports lifelong participation in physical activity (PA) (Association for Physical Education, 2020; Hills et al., 2015). European PE curricula define basic motor competencies (BMC) as the key learning goals for specific grade levels (Herrmann, 2017; Scheuer et al., 2019). However, research indicates substantial variability in BMC among primary school children (Wälti et al., 2022). A significant proportion of children fail to achieve the minimum requirements for their grade levels in PE, indicating a need for educational motor support (De Meester et al., 2018; Herrmann et al., 2021). Therefore, it is of great importance to understand the correlates and determinants of motor competence and specifically BMC to effectively support children in their motor development (Lopes et al., 2021). While individual factors influencing motor competence have been extensively studied, the relationship between BMC and school-specific aspects, such as the practice of PE

curriculum tools like timetables and allocated subject time, remains largely unexplored (Pill & Harvey, 2019). Additionally, there is a paucity of data concerning the interaction between these school-specific variables and individual factors in relation to BMC. The present study aims to address these research gaps by assessing the relationship between BMC and the allocated time to PE.

As part of the main learning goals in European PE curricula, BMC are functional performance dispositions which serve as the foundation for participation in the sports culture and for further motor learning (Herrmann et al., 2019). The construct of BMC aligns with the concept of physical literacy and belongs to motor competence, which is often used as an umbrella term for terminologies like motor proficiency, motor performance, and fundamental movement skills. These concepts describe goal-oriented movements that involve fine and gross motor skills, coordination, and whole-body movements (L. E. Robinson et al., 2015; Utesch & Bardid, 2019). Achieving BMC depends on general motor abilities (e.g., fitness), specific motor skills (e.g., slapshot

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technique), as well as motivational and cognitive factors (Herrmann et al., 2016), which are also key traits of physical literacy (Corbin, 2016; Whitehead, 2010). BMC further reflect the competence-oriented approach in European educational science, focusing on monitoring PE learning outcomes (Klieme & Hartig, 2007; Scheuer et al., 2019; Weinert, 2001). Therefore, BMC assessments are aligned with PE curricula in primary school (Scheuer et al., 2019). This differentiates BMC from other motor concepts.

PE provides the foundation for access to and systematic promotion of a healthy lifestyle (Ramires et al., 2023; UNESCO, 2015). During the school day, PE is the only context in which all children experience regular, protected, and supervised PA promotion (Bailey et al., 2022). PE reduces inactivity and sedentary time during days with PE classes and contributes to daily PA. As numerous children fail to attain the WHO recommendations of 60 min of daily PA, PE plays a pivotal role in increasing this amount (Mooses et al., 2017). The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) recommends that primary schools provide 150 min of PE per week (UNESCO, 2015).

The weekly amount of PE differs considerably between and within countries (D'Anna et al., 2019; European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2013; D. Robinson et al., 2019). While in many countries, the central education authorities indicate the minimum number of hours allocated to PE during primary school, other countries have no centralised curriculum in their educational system (Naul & Scheuer, 2020). Consequently, the determination of curricular matters is frequently entrusted to local educational authorities like school districts or principals (Dudley & Burden, 2020). Over the past two decades, the amount of time allocated to PE in many European countries notably declined, with many schools now offering only two lessons (of 45 min each) or less (Naul & Scheuer, 2020). Therefore, a considerable proportion of children are falling below the recommended levels of PE. Furthermore, a significant amount of PE time is allocated to changing, observing demonstrations and receiving instructions, rather than to physical activity itself (Hollis et al., 2016). Consequently, there have been several calls for increased PE as well as extracurricular PA, given that participation in sports clubs and extracurricular PA also contribute significantly to achieving daily PA recommendations (EU-expert group on health-enhancing physical activity, 2015; Kokko et al., 2019). The principle that more PE time equals better outcomes is widely accepted, as more time means more opportunities for practice and learning (D. Robinson et al., 2019).

However, previous studies have yielded inconsistent results regarding the amount of PE and the achievement of PE learning goals or motor competence. Children who participated in daily PE during primary school exhibited fewer motor skill deficits and higher grades in PE than children who participated in only two lessons of PE per week (Ericsson & Karlsson, 2014). Additionally, they demonstrated superior cognitive abilities and fitness performance compared to children who received only 45 min of PE per week (Reed et al., 2013). Consequently, it can be assumed that the decline in PE due to cuts in favour of other subjects or the generally low volume of PE in some countries may be partly responsible for poor results in the learning goals of PE, such as BMC (UNESCO, 2014). Conversely, two meta-analyses on the effect of PE on overall motor competence and fundamental movement skills revealed that only quality- or curriculum-based interventions led to improvements in motor competence, but not quantity-based interventions that increased the frequency or duration of PE (García-Hermoso et al., 2020; Loràs, 2020). Nevertheless, these studies and meta-analyses were experimental intervention studies that focused on a specific region of assessment and did not address the regular PE time. Despite the extensive and diverse research on the effects of PE on various motor aspects, the association between different amounts of PE and BMC has not yet been investigated.

One reason for the differences in BMC levels is the association with *individual endogenous factors* such as the children's age (older children have higher BMC levels than younger children), their sex (boys tend to perform better in object movement tasks than girls), and their weight status (children with a high body-mass-index [BMI] generally show lower BMC levels than children with a lower BMI) (Barnett et al., 2016; Herrmann et al., 2019; Strotmeyer et al., 2020). Furthermore, children who participate in club or recreational sports outside of school (which is considered as an *individual exogenous factor*) demonstrate higher levels of BMC (Pill & Harvey, 2019; Strotmeyer et al., 2020; Wälti et al., 2023). In addition to the aforementioned individual factors, several *school- or system-related factors* (also known as *structural factors*) may contribute to the observed differences in motor competence across countries, as highlighted by multinational studies. These include differences in governmental strategies to promote PA (Laukkanen et al., 2020) or in local sports culture and sports policy (Haga et al., 2018). As BMC belong to the key objectives of PE curricula in many countries, most studies attribute differences to the school-specific PE context and content, curricula, and the structural framework of schools (Bardid et al., 2015; Haga et al., 2018; Luz et al., 2019).

In light of the aforementioned uncertainty within this field of research, this paper attempts to elucidate the relationship between the time allocated to PE as a structural factor of PE and BMC by analysing a large European sample of primary school children. The main aim is to investigate whether differences in BMC levels are associated with different amounts of weekly PE. It is hypothesised that children who receive more PE time demonstrate superior BMC levels compared to those with less PE, as they have more opportunities to engage in practice.

Methods

Sample and procedure

The cross-sectional study was part of an international collaborative project involving thirteen institutions from twelve European countries. The project's objective was to investigate BMC in convenient samples in their respective regions (Salzburg – Austria, Liège – Belgium, Brno – Czech Republic, Frankfurt – Germany, Potsdam/Berlin – Germany, Athens – Greece, Foggia – Italy, Kaunas – Lithuania, Luxembourg – Luxembourg, Groningen – the Netherlands, Lisbon – Portugal, Trnava – Slovakia, Zurich – Switzerland). The assessments were conducted during the second half of 2018. Prior to the assessment, all project partners obtained ethical clearance and written informed consent from the children's legal guardians for their sample. Verbal consent was obtained from the children prior to their participation in the study. All research procedures were conducted in accordance with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments or comparable ethical standards.

Data assessments per class were conducted during a single regular PE lesson. The eight stations of the BMC test instrument were set up in the sports hall. The classes were divided into groups of four to five children, with

each group being led by a test leader who had undergone specialised training. For each BMC test item, the test leader provided a brief explanation and a single demonstration of the task at each station. At a distinct station, the test leader conducted a body weight and height assessment and an interview with each child regarding their extracurricular physical activities. The order of the stations was randomly determined by each test leader. Children with incomplete anthropometric data assessments due to insufficient time were excluded from the analyses. The final data set comprised $N = 4721$ 6- to 10-year-old primary school children with complete data for all independent variables and at least one BMC area. Table 1 provides details on the composition of the final sample.

Instruments

Basic motor competencies

BMC were measured using the MOBAK-1–2 for 6- to 8-year-old children and the MOBAK-3–4 for 8- to 10-year-old children with standardised material according to the test manual, with both instruments covering two grade levels (Herrmann, 2018; Herrmann & Seelig, 2017; Herrmann et al., 2015).¹ The psychometric quality criteria for the MOBAK-1–2 and MOBAK-3–4 were repeatedly confirmed in various validation studies using confirmatory factor analysis (Herrmann, 2018; Herrmann & Seelig, 2017; Herrmann et al., 2015). The test instrument was selected for each class according to the regular age of the respective grade level. The test manuals and protocols were available in the respective language of the assessment region. Each instrument covers two motor competence areas with four items each: *object movement* (OM) with the items throwing, catching, bouncing, dribbling, and *self-movement* (SM) with the items balancing, rolling, jumping and running. The test instruments only differ in the difficulty and complexity of the test

Table 1. Sample composition.

Region	MOBAK-1–2 age group		MOBAK-3–4 age group	
	Children	Classes	Children	Classes
Austria	188	11	211	13
Belgium	299	15		
Czech Republic	172	8	253	13
Germany Frankfurt	848	49		
Germany Potsdam	438	26		
Greece	128	9	168	11
Italy			279	13
Lithuania	30	2	56	4
Luxembourg	243	18		
Netherlands	150	9	68	4
Portugal	94	7	86	6
Slovakia	104	7	185	11
Switzerland	126	9	165	11
Total sample	2820	170	1471	86

items. Both are aligned with several national PE curricula in Europe (Gerlach et al., 2018). Consensus was reached by local PE experts from each country on the content-related validity of the test instrument in relation to their respective curricula. In the six items dribbling, bouncing, rolling, balancing, jumping and running, children had two attempts (no trial run) each, with a break between the two attempts. For each attempt, the test leader recorded whether it was a failed or a passed attempt (failed attempt = 0 points; passed attempt = 1 point). The scores from both attempts were later added per item. In the items throwing and catching, the children had six consecutive attempts each, and successful attempts were recorded on the protocol and later transformed into points (0–2 successful attempts = 0 points; 3–4 successful attempts = 1 point; 5–6 successful attempts = 2 points). With a maximum of two points per item, a total of 8 points per competence area can be achieved.

Endogenous factors of the child

The test leader noted the age (by month and year of birth) and sex of each child on the protocol. Body height (in cm, rounded up or down to whole numbers and later converted to m) was assessed using measuring tape. Body weight (in kg, rounded up or down to whole numbers) was measured with a scale. Later on, these data were utilised to calculate BMI ($\text{mass}(\text{kg})/\text{height}^2(\text{m}^2)$). All analyses that included BMI values were adjusted for age and sex.

Exogenous factors of the child

The test leader asked each child about the participation in any kind of regular weekly sport activities outside of school and classified the response according to the following categories: ball sports, racket sports, endurance-oriented activities, and coordination-oriented activities (e.g., gymnastics, athletics, martial arts, dancing). The answer was recorded on the protocol. For the purposes of analyses, responses were later on divided into two variables according to the BMC areas SM and OM, namely individual sports (summarising endurance-oriented activities, racket sports and coordination-oriented activities; no participation in any of these = 0, participation in at least one of these = 1) and ball sports (ball sports; no participation = 0, participation = 1).

Structural school factor

The time allocation for PE (How much time [in minutes] is provided for one lesson at your school? How many PE lessons per week are given in this class [1 to 6 lessons]?) was evaluated via a questionnaire administered to the teachers in each class. The total

amount of PE per week in minutes was calculated by multiplying the length of one lesson by the number of lessons per week.

Data analyses

Classes with less than ten children with valid data were excluded from the analyses to avoid bias in multilevel analyses. Separate analyses were conducted for children aged 6- to 8- years old (tested with the MOBAK-1–2, referred as MOBAK-1–2 age group) and children aged 8- to 10-years-old (tested with the MOBAK-3–4, referred as MOBAK-3–4 age group). The age cut-off values were determined according to the age range of each test instrument and the time of assessment (MOBAK-1–2: 5.92–8.25 years; MOBAK-3–4: 7.92–10.25 years). Descriptive statistics (mean, standard error, and 95 % confidence interval (CI)) for all variables are shown in Table 2. Linear relationships between OM, SM, ball sport and individual sport participation as well as the amount of weekly PE were calculated using partial Pearson correlations, which were corrected for age, sex, and BMI.

A multilevel regression approach was conducted to determine whether, apart from endogenous and exogenous individual factors, the amount of time allocated to PE predicted student achievements in OM or SM. First, two-level null models (child – class) without predictors were estimated for OM and SM to calculate the amount of total variation in BMC levels explained by the classes. Second, endogenous (sex, age, BMI) and exogenous (ball sport and individual sport participation) level 1 variables were included in the models for OM and SM to examine the characteristics of the children. Sex, ball sports and individual sports were entered as dichotomous variables (sex: 0 = boy; 1 = girl; ball/individual sports: 0 = no participation; 1 = participation); age and BMI were entered as continuous variables. Third, the structural level 2 variable (weekly amount of PE) was added to obtain the complete models.

All model parameters were simultaneously estimated using restricted maximum likelihood procedures. Variables were grand mean centred in all analyses, with the exception of the cross-level-interaction analyses, where the level 1 predictors ball sports and individual sports were group-mean centred as suggested by Enders and Tofighi (2007). Akaike Information Criterion and R^2 were provided as values for the goodness-of-fit of the models. Unless otherwise indicated, $p < 0.05$ and 95 % CI that do not include zero were considered to be statistically significant. All statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 29 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) and jamovi 2.3.18 (The jamovi project, 2023).

Results

Sample characteristics

The data set of children tested with the MOBAK-1–2 comprises 2820 children from 170 classes and twelve countries with an age range of 5.92–8.25 years (Table 2). Using the MOBAK-3–4, a total of 1471 children between 7.92–10.25 years of age from 86 classes and nine countries were tested and included in the analyses. Sex distribution was equal in both age groups. In both data sets, more children participated in individual sports than in ball sports. In the group with the 8- to 10-year-old children, more children participated in extracurricular PA of both types than children in the MOBAK-1–2 age group. The mean time allocated to PE was 110 min in the MOBAK-1–2 age group (range: 45–360 min) and 95 min in the MOBAK-3–4 age group (range: 30–270 min). In both age groups, the modal and median values for weekly PE time were 90 min. Children achieved higher BMC values in SM than in OM in both age groups (Table 2).

Regression analyses

Pre-analyses accounting for differences in endogenous variables indicated that ball sport participation, individual sport participation, and the amount of PE were positively correlated with OM and SM in both age groups, with small effect sizes. Consequently, participation in extracurricular PA as well as a higher amount of PE were associated to higher BMC levels. The amount of PE was positively correlated with ball sport participation in the MOBAK-1–2 age group and with individual sport participation in the MOBAK-3–4 age group, although the effect sizes were low. The findings indicated that children from the MOBAK-1–2 age group with higher amounts of PE were more likely to engage in ball sports, whereas children in the MOBAK-3–4 age group with higher amounts of PE tended to participate in individual sports.

The results of the hierarchical regression analyses are presented for the MOBAK-1–2 age group in Table 3 (OM in model 1, SM in model 2) and for the MOBAK-3–4 age group in Table 4 (OM in model 3, SM in model 4). The intraclass correlations (ICC) from the null models indicated effects of the class level on portions of explained variances in both age groups and competence areas. The ICC showed that 12.3% of the variance in OM and 20.8% of the variance in SM in the MOBAK-1–2 age group, and 24.0% of the variance in OM and 34.0% of the variance in SM in the MOBAK-3–4 age group were situated at the class level.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of endogenous and exogenous factors, weekly amount of physical education and basic motor competencies.

Age group	Endogenous factors			Exogenous factors			Structural factor			Basic motor competencies				
	Sex	Age	BMI	Ball sport participation ^a	Individual sport participation ^a	Amount of PE ^b	Object movement	Self-movement	Mean	SE	95 % CI	Mean	SE	95 % CI
MOBAK-1–2 (N = 2820)	Girls 50 %	Mean 6.85 SE 0.01 95 % CI [6.84, 6.88]	Mean 15.99 SE 0.04 95 % CI [15.90, 16.07]	Mean 32.4 % SE 0.9 95 % CI [30.7, 34.1]	Mean 55.3 % SE 0.9 95 % CI [53.5, 57.2]	Mean 109.8 SE 0.8 95 % CI [108.2, 111.5]	Mean 4.34 SE 0.04 95 % CI [4.26, 4.41]	Mean 5.00 SE 0.04 95 % CI [4.92, 5.07]	2758	2785	2758	2758	2758	2758
MOBAK-3–4 (N = 1471)	Girls 50 %	Mean 9.18 SE 0.01 95 % CI [9.15, 9.21]	Mean 17.40 SE 0.08 95 % CI [17.24, 17.55]	Mean 43.6 % SE 1.3 95 % CI [41.1, 46.2]	Mean 69.0 % SE 1.2 95 % CI [66.6, 71.4]	Mean 95.4 SE 1.1 95 % CI [93.3, 97.4]	Mean 3.89 SE 0.06 95 % CI [3.78, 4.01]	Mean 4.01 SE 0.06 95 % CI [3.90, 4.12]	1463	1463	1463	1457	1457	1457

Abbreviations: CI confidence interval; N sample size; SE standard error. ^a No participation = 0, participation = 1. ^b in minutes.

Table 3. Multilevel modelling results: parameter estimates and variance components for basic motor competencies assessed with the MOBAK-1–2, stratified by competence area.

Object movement MOBAK-1–2 age group								
	Model 1a				Model 1b			
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Level 1 (2785 cases)								
Intercept	4.33	0.05	85.54	<.001	4.33	0.05	86.59	<.001
Sex ^a	–1.09	0.07	–15.12	<.001	–1.09	0.07	–15.07	<.001
Age	0.73	0.07	10.11	<.001	0.74	0.07	10.19	<.001
Body mass index	–0.01	0.02	–0.98	0.327	–0.01	0.02	–0.97	0.333
Ball sports ^b	0.75	0.08	9.41	<.001	0.74	0.08	9.34	<.001
Individual sports ^b	0.24	0.07	3.27	0.001	0.23	0.07	3.24	0.001
Level 2 (170 clusters)								
Amount of PE					0.00	0.00	2.30	0.023
AIC		11036.41				11033.12		
<i>R</i> ² (fixed+random effects)		.264				.266		
Self-movement MOBAK-1–2 age group								
	Model 2a				Model 2b			
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Level 1 (2758 cases)								
Intercept	5.00	0.07	76.01	<.001	5.00	0.07	76.23	<.001
Sex ^a	0.36	0.08	4.75	<.001	0.36	0.08	4.78	<.001
Age	0.35	0.08	4.31	<.001	0.35	0.08	4.33	<.001
Body mass index	–0.13	0.02	–8.04	<.001	–0.13	0.02	–8.04	<.001
Ball sports ^b	0.52	0.08	6.11	<.001	0.51	0.08	6.08	<.001
Individual sports ^b	0.50	0.08	6.43	<.001	0.49	0.08	6.43	<.001
Level 2 (169 clusters)								
Amount of PE					0.00	0.00	1.49	0.138
AIC		11186.71				11186.47		
<i>R</i> ² (fixed+random effects)		0.199				0.200		

Abbreviations: AIC = Akaike information criterion; *B* = unstandardized beta; *CI* = confidence interval; PE = physical education; *SE_B* = standard error for the unstandardized beta.

^aboys = 0; girls = 1.

^bno participation = 0, participation = 1.

Table 4. Multilevel modelling results: parameter estimates and variance components for basic motor competencies assessed with the MOBAK-3–4, stratified by competence area.

Object movement MOBAK-3–4 age group								
	Model 3a				Model 3b			
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Level 1 (1463 cases)								
Intercept	3.96	0.11	37.38	<.001	3.94	0.10	39.66	<.001
Sex ^a	–1.17	0.10	–11.55	<.001	–1.17	0.10	–11.59	<.001
Age	0.55	0.12	4.63	<.001	0.53	0.12	4.47	<.001
Body mass index	–0.10	0.02	–5.92	<.001	–0.10	0.02	–5.87	<.001
Ball sports ^b	0.84	0.11	7.78	<.001	0.84	0.11	7.76	<.001
Individual sports ^b	0.17	0.12	1.50	0.133	0.17	0.11	1.50	0.135
Level 2 (86 clusters)								
Amount of PE					0.01	0.00	3.54	<.001
AIC		5950.98				5940.98		
<i>R</i> ² (fixed+random effects)		0.343				0.351		
Self-movement MOBAK-3–4 age group								
	Model 4a				Model 4b			
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Level 1 (1457 cases)								
Intercept	4.07	0.11	35.71	<.001	4.03	0.10	39.36	<.001
Sex ^a	0.36	0.10	3.78	<.001	0.37	0.10	3.81	<.001
Age	0.46	0.12	3.97	<.001	0.45	0.11	3.93	<.001
Body mass index	–0.13	0.02	–8.23	<.001	–0.13	0.02	–8.20	<.001

(Continued)

Table 4. (Continued).

	Model 4a				Model 4b			
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE_B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Ball sports ^b	0.46	0.10	4.47	<.001	0.48	0.10	4.62	<.001
Individual sports ^b	0.61	0.11	5.56	<.001	0.63	0.11	5.73	<.001
Level 2 (86 clusters)								
Amount of PE					0.01	0.00	4.49	<.001
AIC			5793.51				5777.00	
<i>R</i> ² (fixed+random effects)			0.327				0.341	

Abbreviations: AIC = Akaike information criterion; *B* = unstandardized beta; *CI* = confidence interval; PE = physical education; *SE_B* = standard error for the unstandardized beta.

^aboys = 0; girls = 1.

^bno participation = 0, participation = 1.

Of the endogenous variables, sex and age were significantly related to BMC levels in both competence areas and both age groups (models 1a – 4a). In both age groups, boys exhibited higher levels in OM tasks than girls. Older children in the MOBAK-1–2 age group performed better in OM and SM than their younger peers, which was also the case in the MOBAK-3–4 age group. A higher BMI was negatively related to SM in the MOBAK-1–2 age group (model 2a) and to both motor competence areas in the MOBAK-3–4 age group (models 3a and 4a), indicating that children with a lower BMI reached higher scores in BMC. Participation in ball sports was positively associated with OM and SM in both age groups (models 1a – 4a), and individual sport participation was positively related to SM in both age groups and to OM in the MOBAK-1–2 age group (models 1a, 2a, 4a). Although the model fits improved in all models, the proportion of explained variance increased with the addition of the endogenous and exogenous factors only in the OM models (models 1a and 3a), while it decreased in the SM models (models 2a and 4a). Upon the addition of the level 2 variable ‘class’ to the models (models 1b – 4b), the amount of explained variance increased in all models. In both the MOBAK-1–2 and MOBAK-3–4 age groups, no correlations were observed between the amount of PE and OM or SM.

Discussion

In order to provide support for children in their motor development, it is essential to gain an understanding of the correlates and determinants of this process. Given that only individual aspects have been investigated in their relationship with BMC so far, the aim of this study was to analyse the relationship between the structural factor weekly allocated PE time, and BMC. Contrary to the initial hypothesis, no association was found between the weekly amount of PE time and BMC. The amount of weekly PE

does not appear to affect children’s BMC levels when controlling for endogenous and exogenous variables.

As in previous studies, sex, age, BMI, and participation in extracurricular PA were significant predictors of both OM and SM in both age groups (Herrmann et al., 2019). With regard to the structural factor of the amount of weekly PE, overall BMC levels seem to be independent of whether children receive a lower or higher amount of PE. Despite the paucity of research on the correlation between instructional time in PE and movement competence, a small number of studies offer further insights.

The mean amount of PE was 110 min in the MOBAK-1–2 age group and 95 min in the MOBAK-3–4 age group. This goes in line with the reduction of the time allocated to PE to 90 min per week in a considerable number of European countries (Naul & Scheuer, 2020). The absence of observable associations between the amount of PE and BMC could be attributed to the limited variance in PE time across classes (95% CIs: 108.2–111.5 and 93.3–97.4 min; see Table 2). In a longitudinal study, Swedish children in the first through ninth grades of primary school participated in five PE lessons per week (225 min) and, if necessary, additional weekly adapted motor training. The results demonstrated that these children performed better in object control and locomotor skills than children who attended two weekly PE lessons (90 min) (Ericsson, 2014; Ericsson & Karlsson, 2014). The authors of the study concluded that two weekly PE lessons are insufficient to stimulate children’s development of motor skills. Therefore, it may be assumed that only a substantially higher amount of weekly PE is sufficient to elicit measurable associations with BMC. Conversely, in an adolescent population, an augmentation in PE from 150 min to 250 min per week did not yield a greater enhancement in motor performance over time (Reif et al., 2021). The authors of the study hypothesised that this may be indicative of a ceiling effect in motor performance which was reached

earlier by the intervention group, which could explain the observed outcomes. Future studies should investigate whether a threshold exists at which PE time becomes an effective determinant of BMC.

The considerable proportion of variance explained by participation in extracurricular PA implies that how children spend their free time plays a greater role than how much PE they receive at school. These results reflect those of a previous study, which found that adolescents with a sports club membership demonstrated higher motor performance scores than those without, irrespective of the amount of weekly PE lessons (Reif et al., 2021). Polish first-grade children who participated in 45 min of extracurricular sports per week offered by their school had significantly better motor skills after one year than their peers who did not participate in these activities (Skowroński et al., 2019). It is therefore of great importance to provide easy access to extracurricular PA and to enable children to participate in such activities.

While the present study solely considered the quantity of time allocated to PE, it is known from the offer-use model of instruction and other related works that several factors influence the delivery of PE programmes and the achievement of learning goals (Helmke, 2021; D. Robinson et al., 2019). Quality- or curriculum-based PE interventions were found to be effective in improving motor competence, whereas the total time for PE interventions did not moderate the effect of PE on motor competence (García-Hermoso et al., 2020; Lorås, 2020). Initial research on the relevance of teacher characteristics and attitudes on BMC implies that teachers' goal orientation may be related to BMC (Schole et al., 2022). Consequently, it can be assumed that these factors may play a more significant role in the achievement of BMC than the amount of PE.

This study is characterised by several strengths. It was the first hierarchical analysis of potential associations between structural factors and BMC and their interplay with individual correlates. The large European sample allowed further investigation into overarching determinants of children's differing BMC levels and provided a foundation for future research. By focusing on the amount of time allocated to PE, calls for quantitative research that should take into account the actual PE practise and consider 'the education policy and curriculum structures within which the teaching for student achievement of outcomes and standards related to movement competence occurs' were addressed (Pill & Harvey, 2019, p. 53).

The scope of this study was limited by the absence of additional structural and class level factors of PE and only focusing on the amount of allocated time. Future

studies should consider further aspects of teaching that are responsible for students' learning outcomes, such as the teacher's knowledge, goals and motivation, the quality of teaching, or the context of the school. Further on, no consideration was given to variations in the availability or popularity of extracurricular sport activities in the different regions. Despite the considerable range of weekly PE time observed in both age groups, only a small number of classes exhibited largely disparate amounts of PE time. The specificities of the national curricula were not taken into account. Nevertheless, PE experts from each country concurred on the content-related validity of the test instrument in relation to their respective curricula. The cross-sectional design of the study does not allow for any causal interpretation into the dynamics of individual and structural relationships on BMC values. Another limitation of this study is the sole examination of two specific areas of motor competence, namely self-movement and object movement. Although these areas cover a significant proportion of BMC in primary school, they do not represent the full range of children's motor competence, what limits the generalisability of the study results.

In conclusion, this study found that, despite previous evidence of positive effects of higher amounts of PE on cognitive and affective aspects of student learning and academic performance, the weekly amount of PE was not associated with BMC levels in 6- to 10-year-old primary school children in Europe. Other school-specific or PE-related factors might be more crucial for differences in BMC levels than the amount of PE. These findings underscore the necessity to more closely examine the characteristics of PE and the contributions of teachers to PE in order to elucidate the discrepancies in BMC levels between European countries. Given the evidence that extracurricular physical activity is a relevant factor for BMC, it is recommended that efforts are made to ensure that as many children as possible participate in extracurricular sports.

Note

1. See mobak.info for a description of the test objects and demonstration videos.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [MW], upon reasonable request.

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